

Local Thermal Resistance Extraction in Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits

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Abstract—The thermal resistance of a High Electron Mobility Transistor (HEMT) forming part of a Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC) is non-invasively extracted under real working conditions (electrical and thermal) by infrared thermal imaging. The HEMT thermal resistance considers the device local maximum temperature and dissipated power. An experimental approach to this end is currently not available, as the HEMTs thermal interaction does not allow extracting its individual heat generation. Thanks to thermal field confinement offered by heat source frequency modulation, the power dissipation in each device is inferred, making feasible its individual thermal resistance extraction. As a result, reasonable values of the local thermal resistance of each individual HEMT integrated in the MMIC (i.e., 57.8 ± 3.4 °C/W and 24.8 ± 1.4 °C/W) are obtained in agreement with studies on discrete devices available in the literature.

Index Terms— Lock-in Thermography, MMIC, functional characterization.

I. INTRODUCTION

MONOLITHIC Microwave Integrated Circuits (MMICs) play a key role in size-constrained and low power electronic systems for aerospace, defense, and industrial applications, such as microwave radio [1] [2], electronic warfare [3] [4], and unmanned aerial vehicles [5] [6], respectively. In all them, MMICs operate as amplifiers (low-noise or power), microwave mixers, or high-frequency switches [7] within communication [1] [7], navigation [8] [9], or advanced radar detection systems [2] [10]. In this scenario, they have replaced the bulkier, higher

voltage-biased and more expensive vacuum tube-based systems, as MMIC-based approaches offer more attractive, compact, reliable, and lower voltage-biased solutions [2].

To cope with such demanding appliances, MMICs require of fast and reliable active devices commonly developed with III-V semiconductors (e.g., Gallium Arsenide; GaAs). Initially, Metal-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors (MESFETs) were used, but recently, High Electron Mobility Transistors (HEMT) and pseudomorphic-HEMTs (p-HEMTs) have gained major attention, demonstrating a power capacity of up to 10 W per MMIC [2]. HEMTs and p-HEMTs are heterojunction transistors made with materials presenting similar and different lattice constants, respectively [11]. As a result, p-HEMTs show a larger band gap difference, and provide a better performance than HEMTs [11]. Unfortunately, both transistors experience a high self-heating and due to the substrate low thermal conductivity, their operating temperature may locally extremely raise. This degrades the MMIC performance [12], or eventually, produces the die burn-out when the substrate thermal limit is overcome [13]. Besides, the continuous scaling down of p-HEMTs [14], [15] worsens even more this operating landscape. Therefore, countermeasures based on thermal management strategies are currently under research [16], jointly with new experimental methodologies for their local appraisal.

Traditionally, a common solution to assess the improvement achieved by any thermal management approach is the thermal resistance measurement using electrical thermo-sensitive parameters (TSPs) [17]. TSPs provide an indirect evaluation of an averaged MMIC junction temperature (T_J^{TSP}). The same occurs with the thermal resistance measurements based on standard JEDEC rules [18]. An average thermal resistance junction-to-case ($\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$) is determined as follows: the difference between T_J^{TSP} and case temperature (T_C , packaging backside or case) divided by the total dissipated power (P_{tot}). From a reliability point of view, a thermal resistance accounting for the maximum semiconductor temperature value is more interesting, as not only the MMIC maximum operating temperature is directly determined, but also, as performed in discrete HEMTs, the allowable power dissipation [19]. Regrettably, the existing techniques do not permit locally measuring in each device either its average power consumption (P_i) or its maximum local temperature ($T_{j,i}^{MAX}$), which makes impossible the maximum local thermal resistance ($R_{TH(J-C),i}$)

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extraction in MMIC devices. Notice that $R_{\text{TH}(J-C),i}$ may become an important design parameter to rapidly determine the maximum operating temperature in the case of HEMT-based MMICs. However, this is not currently available in research or mass production labs neither in intelligent manufacturing plants (industry 4.0 processes).

In last decades, off-chip methods have appeared to thermally characterize integrated circuits (ICs) at die level [20]. They perform spatially-resolved measurements of temperature dependent parameters; e.g., resistance [21], refractive index [22], or thermal radiation [23], [24], [25], [26]; and show a great potential for MMIC thermal analysis. However, with off-chip measurements in the time domain, the thermal interaction among all MMIC parts cannot always be avoided, and determining the local power consumption per component is not feasible. In contrast, thermal analysis in the frequency domain can prevent the thermal interaction between them [27], [28]. When a heat source is modulated at a fixed frequency f_0 , the temperature field confines around it as f_0 increases, and heat sources do not thermally interact. This allows individually measuring them regardless of the external boundary conditions by lock-in detection strategies with a higher sensitivity and robustness to noise [24]. Moreover, other spectral components different to f_0 are suppressed. Thus, weak heat sources ($< 1 \text{ m}^\circ\text{C}$ usually) can be studied [24].

As a response to this clear industrial need, this work aims at presenting a solution to determine $R_{\text{TH}(J-C),i}$ of p-HEMTs integrated in a MMIC based on an infrared (IR) thermographic system performing thermal acquisitions in both time and frequency domains. This approach takes advantage of local temperature measurement in time domain (devices thermally interacting) and power dissipation per device extraction in frequency domain (no devices thermal interaction), being entirely incorporable in mass production environments for non-invasive off-chip testing by imaging-based automatic inspection and analysis systems [29]. To assess its feasibility, the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the IR Lock-in Thermography (IR-LIT) is presented. The theoretical basis for $R_{\text{TH}(J-C),i}$ determination is described in Section III. Section IV refers to the used test vehicles and the followed experimental procedure. Section V presents and discusses the results obtained and, finally, Section VI draws the main conclusions of the work.

II. IR-LIT AND HEAT SOURCE THERMAL CONFINEMENT

IR-LIT is based on detecting the IR thermal emission originated from frequency modulated heat sources by using lock-in detection approaches [24]. When several heat sources on the top surface of a semiconductor die dissipate heat following a given periodic waveform with frequency f_0 , they produce a thermal field spectral component at f_0 [24], [28], [30] as:

$$\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t, f_0) = |P_0(f_0)| \sum_{n=1}^N \iint_{S_{\text{HS},n}} dS_{\text{HS},n} \left[a_n \times \frac{C}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_n|} e^{-\phi_{\tau,n}} \cos\left(2\pi f_0 t - \phi_{\tau,n} - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where $|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_n|$ is the distance between each location \vec{r} from the coordinate origin of the thermal field and each heat source or hot spot location (\vec{r}_n), $dS_{\text{HS},n}$ is the differential of surface of the n -th hot spot, and C is a boundary condition constant. $|P_0(f_0)|$ is the amplitude of the total active power dissipated by all heat sources at f_0 . a_n corresponds to a fraction of $|P_0(f_0)|$ dissipated in each heat source. $\phi_{\tau,n}$ is the thermal phase lag related with the heat propagation around a given n -th heat source, defined as:

$$\phi_{\tau,n} = \frac{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_n|}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the thermal diffusion characteristic length and writes as:

$$\rho = \sqrt{\frac{D}{\pi f_0}} \quad (3)$$

where D corresponds to the thermal diffusivity of the media. ρ fixes the external boundary condition when the die thickness h is considered ($\rho < h$, thermally thick condition) [31]. Here, $\phi_{\tau,n}$ only depends on D , f_0 and $|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_n|$. Therefore, following a lock-in detection strategy, $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t, f_0)$ can be sensed. As a result, the thermal amplitude ($|\Delta T|$) and phase lag images of $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t, f_0)$ are derived, in a similar way to steady state frequency analysis in signal processing [24]. This technique shows a very high spatial resolution to determine hot spots on the device surface, as $\Delta T(\vec{r}, \vec{r}_n, t, f_0)$ confines around the hot spot when f_0 increases [24] according to the exponential decay in the thermal amplitude depicted in (1).

III. $R_{\text{TH}(J-C),i}$ MEASUREMENT THEORETICAL APPROACH

Usually, radio-frequency (RF) integrated transistors are formed by the parallel connection of several interdigitated structures with the drain and source terminals placed along the gate contact, called gate fingers. Each gate finger sets within the transistor a conduction channel area A_f (i.e., finger active area) and, in turn, a heat source, also ensuring an equal current sharing among them while the transistor operates at RF. According to this layout structure, $R_{\text{TH}(J-C),i}$ for a given i -th transistor has been defined in Section I as the ratio between its maximum junction-to-case temperature increase ΔT_i and its average dissipated power P_i . ΔT_i can be determined from IR thermal measurements in the time domain, but this is not the case for P_i . To properly extract P_i , such devices should be under real operating conditions, i.e., electrical and biasing (both voltage and temperature), without thermally interacting among them. This makes its measurement a real challenge. To address this, concepts of heat source frequency modulation and IR-LIT monitoring can be exploited for P_i determination thanks to the RF transistors layout properties, the distance among them in the MMIC and the easy extraction of the total MMIC dissipated power P_{tot} . In terms of P_i , P_{tot} can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{i=1}^s P_i \quad (4)$$

where s is the total number of transistors integrated in the MMIC. Owing to IR-LIT measurements at a modulation frequency f_0 , it is possible to confine the thermal field around

Fig. 1. Photograph of an integrated MMIC model CHA5350-99F with its five p-HEMTs transistors (a) and its equivalent simplified schematic circuit (b) extracted from [32].

Fig. 2. Photograph of the MMIC packaged on a Kovar (a) and CuMo (b) substrate, allowing visual top access to the die for IR measurements.

TABLE I
LIST OF PACKAGES AND DIE-ATTACHES USED IN EACH MMIC

MMIC-ID	Package	Die-attach
MMIC-1	Kovar	UNIMEC XH9889-1
MMIC-2	CuMo	UNIMEC XH9889-1
MMIC-3	Kovar	UNIMEC XH9890-6A
MMIC-4	Kovar	UNIMEC XH9890-6S
MMIC-5	Kovar	Au/Sn 80/20
MMIC-6	Kovar	Ablebond 84-1 LMI

the heat sources of each transistor, avoiding their thermal interaction. Under such a situation, P_i can be inferred from the relationship between the average power density \mathcal{P}_j dissipated by a gate finger j with the amplitude of its average thermal increase $|\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}|$, i. e.:

$$P_i = \mathcal{P}_j A_i = \frac{n_i A_f |\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}|}{|T_j(\vec{r}_j, f_0)|} \quad (5)$$

where n_i refers to the total number of fingers of an i -th device and relates A_f with the transistor total active area A_i , as $A_i = n_i A_f$. $|T_j(\vec{r}_j, f_0)| = |\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}|/\mathcal{P}_j$ is the thermal transfer function of a gate finger j , only depending on the distance among fingers $|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_j|$ and the frequency f_0 (system geometry). In turn, $|T_j(\vec{r}_j, f_0)|$ fix the associated temperature field shape and allow determining whether devices thermally interact among them or not. Then, when a frequency f_0 is chosen so that the thermal field is confined around the heat source, thermal coupling between devices is avoided, as previously inferred from (1). From (4) and (5), \mathcal{P}_j can be finally written as function of P_{tot} as:

$$\mathcal{P}_j = \frac{P_{\text{tot}}}{\sum_{i=1}^S \left(\frac{n_i |\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}| |T_j(\vec{r}_j, f_0)|}{|\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}| |T_i(\vec{r}_i, f_0)|} \right) A_f} \quad (6)$$

where the same dissipation is assumed in all fingers, as confirmed further on.

As a matter of fact, \mathcal{P}_j can be considered the power density per device, since: i) the heat generation in the fingers is extremely confined, ii) there are nanometer thin layers on its top (no thermal blurring effect), and iii) the drain current I_D is uniformly distributed within the transistor by design (i.e., equal \mathcal{P}_j per transistor) [33], [34]. Thus, to determine P_i , n_i is required. As a result of these dependences and finger channel behavior, these magnitudes can be measured by IR thermography only using apparent averaged temperature amplitudes $|\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}|$ since $|\overline{\Delta T_{j,i}}| \approx \varepsilon |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}|$ [26], [29], not requiring emissivity correction as ε , in all fingers, is very similar due to all measurements are performed on the same material and surface texture. This allows to cancel ε in (6) simplifying the measurement process. Then, \mathcal{P}_j writes as:

$$\mathcal{P}_j = \frac{P_{\text{tot}}}{\sum_{i=1}^S \left(\frac{n_i |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}| |T_j(\vec{r}_j, f_0)|}{|\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}| |T_i(\vec{r}_i, f_0)|} \right) A_f} \quad (7)$$

By substituting (5) into (7), the fraction of the power dissipated in a given k -th device P_k/P_{tot} with an area A_k and n_k gate fingers can be inferred as:

$$\frac{P_k}{P_{\text{tot}}} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^S \left(\frac{n_i |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}| |T_k(\vec{r}_k, f_0)|}{n_k |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},k}}| |T_i(\vec{r}_i, f_0)|} \right)} \quad (8)$$

In this regard, the subscript k refers to the transistor itself, whereas subscript i identifies its gate fingers. Choosing f_0 low enough to avoid thermal interaction and keep the real working conditions without undesired high-frequency effects (e.g., electrical reflections or performance degradation), P_k/P_{tot} is kept constant. Moreover, when no thermal interaction occurs and heat generation is uniform, (8) simplifies to:

$$\frac{P_k}{P_{\text{tot}}} \approx \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^S \left(\frac{n_i |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},i}}|}{n_k |\overline{\Delta T_{\text{app},k}}|} \right)} \quad (9)$$

By using (9), the power dissipated in each individual transistor may be extracted with the aid of lock-in measurements. In fact, $|\Delta T_{app,j}|$ is calculated according to a procedure based on a two steps average on the apparent thermal amplitude image $|\Delta T_{app}|$. First, a longitudinal temperature average is performed along each finger, also determining the temperature deviation value. Next, the average value per finger is determined by each p-HEMT, as follows: all apparent temperatures per finger are summed up and divided by the device finger number. To have an idea of the values dispersion among fingers of the same device, the standard deviation is also calculated in this second step. Notice that proceeding like this, an idea on the error on P_i is also estimated, where non uniform dissipations or thermal interaction within the device are also accounted for.

After this first step, ΔT_i is extracted as follows. The true temperature map is extracted to determine $T_{j,i}^{MAX}$ for a given electrical and thermal biasing conditions. From now on, P_k and (P_k/P_{tot}) are respectively referred to as P_i and (P_i/P_{tot}) to avoid subscripts misunderstandings. Finally, $R_{TH(j-c),i}$ is calculated as:

$$R_{TH(j-c),i} = \frac{\Delta T_i}{P_i} = \frac{T_{j,i}^{MAX} - T_C}{P_i}, \quad (10)$$

where $T_{j,i}^{MAX}$ is the maximum junction temperature of the semiconductor device i , and T_C , the die backside temperature (measurable with a thermocouple). It is worthy to point out that $T_{j,i}^{MAX}$ is inferred after applying emissivity correction to apparent temperature results [26], [35].

In summary, it is important to notice that the procedure to extract the $R_{TH(j-c),i}$ is a two-step process: firstly, P_i is inferred according to (9) in the frequency domain, and secondly, ΔT_i is measured in the time domain.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

A. Test Vehicles Description

For the test vehicles, commercially available GaAs p-HEMT-based MMICs (CHA5350-99F, for 17-24 GHz) [32] have been used. Fig. 1 shows the MMIC layout (a) and its schematic (b). In this MMIC, five p-HEMTs are connected in parallel with a common gate, drain and source. As a result, only an equivalent single transistor can be externally measured. p-HEMTs 1, 2 and 3 are formed by 8 gate fingers (0.60 mm gate periphery or gate finger total length), p-HEMT 4 has 6 gate fingers (0.45 mm gate periphery) and p-HEMT 5 contains only 4 gate fingers (0.30 mm gate periphery). To have test vehicles with different thermal behavior, several MMICs have been packaged with different die-attach (see Table I) and metallic substrate [Kovar in Fig. 2 (a), and CuMo alloy in Fig. 2 (b)] materials, without covering the dies to ensure their visual access for IR acquisitions with the camera (see Fig. 2). Besides, short bond wires have been used in their packaging to ensure an excellent electrical and thermal behavior of the MMIC. To understand the differences in $\overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$ among test vehicles, Scanning Acoustic Microscope (SAM, Sonoscan Gen-5) inspections have been carried to check the die attach layers. To assess the proposed approach and show its sensitivity, two test

Fig. 3. Experimental test bench.

TABLE II
CALIBRATION COEFFICIENTS OF THE DIFFERENT MMICs, WHERE $T_j^{TSP} = A + B V_{GS} \cdot \overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$ VALUES OF THE CONSIDERED MMICs

MMIC-ID	A (°C)	B (°C/V)	$\overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$ (°C/W)
MMIC-1	512.57	-665.54	6.0
MMIC-2	501.65	-651.64	1.5
MMIC-3	512.43	-665.93	14.0
MMIC-4	512.59	-660.94	9.7
MMIC-5	499.75	-641.37	12.0
MMIC-6	508.94	-665.72	15.7

vehicles with the best thermal performance (lower $\overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$) are enough.

B. Test Vehicles $\overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$ Extraction and TSP Selection

In order to obtain a first insight into the thermal response of the different test vehicles considered in this study, $\overline{R_{TH(j-c)}}$ was obtained for all the MMIC assemblies, considering the parallel connection of the five p-HEMTs as a single equivalent transistor. Among all possible TSPs, e.g., the gate-to-drain voltage (V_{GD}), gate-to-source voltage (V_{GS}), or other electrical magnitudes in discrete AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs [36], [37]; V_{GS} at a constant low gate current (I_G) is the most suitable for this study for the following reasons. Firstly, V_{GS} voltage is easy to monitor in a measuring sub-circuit different from that used to dissipate a given power in the transistors through the Drain terminal. In addition, both sub-circuits share the same reference terminal (the Source). Secondly, the forward voltage drop of rectifying junctions are stable and linear TSPs and p-HEMTs only present a junction in their structure exploitable to this end (gate-to-source Schottky contact). Thirdly, self-heating effect in temperature measurements is avoided for low I_G values [17].

As for the TSP calibration, test vehicles are placed into an oven with a temperature feedback controller, which uses a PT100 1/10 DIN sensor. An acquisition system records V_{GS} dependence on temperature from 25 °C to 90 °C keeping $I_G = 100 \mu A$ to finally infer an analytical relationship between V_{GS} and temperature. Notice that these biasing conditions are only for the TSP calibration and T_j^{TSP} extraction, and do not correspond to those for MMIC normal operation. For a reliable T_j^{TSP} extraction, the TSP calibration must be stable with time. Thus, a burn-in process has been also performed, as usual in GaAs technology [38] (see MIL-STD-883E Method 1015.9), and consisted in annealing the test vehicles in an oven at 125 °C during 96 hours with $I_G=100 \mu A$.

With the selected TSP, $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ has been determined according to the procedure reported in MIL-STD-750E 3100 for discrete transistors [18]. It is worth pointing out that in this test, transistors will not operate at their bias or working point. The measurement process starts when a relatively high I_D is applied (i.e., P is imposed) to heat up the MMIC and T_J^{TSP} is extracted when the device starts to cool down (while $I_G=100\ \mu\text{A}$ with a Keithley 2430), using the following expression:

$$\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}} = \frac{T_J^{TSP} - T_C}{P}, \quad (11)$$

where T_J^{TSP} is inferred after a continuous (steady state) heating at P . T_C is measured with a thermocouple contacting the package backside. More details are provided in [39] (used for thermal analysis in solid-state lighting systems).

C. Test Vehicles Biasing and $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ Measurements

Fig. 3 presents the test bench to thermally and electrically bias the MMICs under their real operating conditions (i.e., $T_C = 75\ \text{°C}$, $P_{\text{tot}} = 1.5\ \text{W}$, $I_D = 300\ \text{mA}$ and $V_{DS} = 5\ \text{V}$), as well as acquire their IR thermal emission. Its main elements are an IR camera (FLIR SC5500) with a G5x microscopic lens ($6\ \mu\text{m}$ lateral resolution), a low jitter noise waveform generator for p-HEMT channel modulation and lock-in synchronization signals (Agilent 33522A), Peltier-thermo-regulated micropositioning stage (i.e., Peltier stage and micropositioner), and a power source (Keithley 2410) for normal operation DC biasing (I_D and V_{DS}). Thermal bias is ensured by placing the test vehicle onto the Peltier stage (see Fig. 3), and thermal grease is used to improve the thermal contact between the package case and the Peltier surface. By calculating T_J^{TSP} , the temperature of the Peltier is tuned to fix $T_C = 75\ \text{°C}$.

As for $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ calculation, P_i and $T_{J,i}^{\text{MAX}}$ are required. To determine P_i by IR-LIT, the heat sources (active transistors) are frequency modulated through the MMIC gate with the Agilent 33522A, while its surface thermal field is recorded with the IR camera. The IR images have been acquired at a frame rate of 376 Hz and with an integration time ranging from 1 to 1.5 ms, leading to 5×10^4 images processed at f_0 . f_0 must be selected so that no thermal interaction between semiconductor devices will be present, i.e., according to (3), $f_0 > 450.5\ \text{Hz}$ is required as: ρ should be shorter than the minimum half distance between devices ($166\ \mu\text{m}$) and $D = 39\ \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$ [40]. Therefore, $f_0 = 497.3\ \text{Hz}$ is set. Once the thermal maps have been obtained, the results are post-processed and P_i/P_{tot} is deduced according to (9) to finally obtain P_i from $|\Delta T_{\text{app},i}|$ results.

After determining P_i , $T_{J,i}^{\text{MAX}}$ is measured in the time domain with the IR-camera, while the MMIC is under its operating biasing point. To do this, several IR thermal images at different temperatures have been acquired to derive the emissivity map of the MMIC by means of post-processing images (emissivity correction) [26]. Next, an IR image of the MMIC biased at its operating point has also been recorded. Post-processing both the biasing image and the emissivity map, the true temperature distribution of the MMIC is finally obtained. With P_i and after determining $T_{J,i}^{\text{MAX}}$, $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ is eventually inferred using (10).

Fig. 4. TSP calibration curves obtained for the different MMICs (a) and burn-in process of MMIC-2 (b).

Fig. 5. SAM images of MMIC-1 (a) and MMIC-2 (b) test vehicles, detailing the MMIC chip area.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ and SAM Results for Test Vehicles

Prior to analyzing $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ results, the linearity and calibration laws of the selected TSP are assessed. Fig. 4 depicts the TSP calibration curves [Fig. 4 (a)] and their stability reached after burn-in [Fig. 4 (b)]. Fig. 4 (a) reports a high linear behavior of V_{GS} at $I_G=100\ \mu\text{A}$ with temperature, as the coefficients resulting from linear fitting demonstrate (see Table II). Besides, a very low variability depending on the analyzed test vehicles is observed. Fig. 4 (b) depicts how the selected TSP becomes stable after a burn-in time of 96 hours. By using (11) and

following the approach detailed in Section IV.B, $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ is determined. Table II also summarizes all $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ results, showing that MMIC-1 (Kovar case) and MMIC-2 (CuMo case) have the lowest $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ (6.0 and 1.5 °C/W, respectively). In both cases, the same die-attach has been used (UNIMEC XH9889-1), as it introduces the lowest $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ with a very low voids density. In the literature, a similar study concerning the thermal behavior of a MESFETs-based GaAs MMIC was published comparing different solutions for die-attach: epoxy and AuSn [41]. In that case, it was demonstrated that the thermal resistance was almost the same for both die-attach materials, supporting that the main contribution to $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ comes from die-attach voids density.

To gain insight into the $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ results and relate them with the die-attach layer, SAM inspections have been performed. In general, SAM results in all test vehicles agree with those derived from $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$: the higher voids density the higher $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ is observed. In Fig. 5, SAM images of MMIC-1 (a) and MMIC-2 are shown. Only voids at the periphery are visible in both cases, which means that they have a low thermal influence. For this reason, MMIC-1 and MMIC-2 are the test vehicles with different $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ selected to assess the proposed approach for $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ measurement.

TABLE III

 $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ AND P_i IN MMIC-1 AND 2 PER P-HEMT

MMIC-ID	$ \Delta T_{app,1} $ (°C)	$ \Delta T_{app,2} $ (°C)	$ \Delta T_{app,3} $ (°C)	$ \Delta T_{app,4} $ (°C)	$ \Delta T_{app,5} $ (°C)
MMIC-1	6.37±0.66	6.44±0.65	7.15±0.78	6.23±0.53	3.90±0.11
MMIC-2	4.27±0.46	4.58±0.60	4.83±0.60	3.67±0.37	3.07±0.21
MMIC-ID	P_1 (mW)	P_2 (mW)	P_3 (mW)	P_4 (mW)	P_5 (mW)
MMIC-1	353±22	357±21	396±23	259±17	108±12
MMIC-2	357±22	382±21	403±23	230±16	128±12

B. $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ Extraction and Assessment

According to the procedure explained in Section IV.C, P_i is first determined setting $f_0 = 497.3$ Hz. To show that this f_0 value allows thermally isolating heat sources without affecting its biasing point, Figs. 6 (a) and (b) show $|\Delta T_{app}|$ maps for MMIC-1 and MMIC-2, respectively. From this figure, it can be inferred that no thermal interaction among devices occurs: $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ confine around each device. Besides, the thermal bias conditions are maintained without experiencing any change, as induced thermal variations (less than 1 °C) are extremely smaller in comparison to the thermal biasing point (75 °C).

With regards to the electrical biasing, no frequency effects are expected in the MMIC electrical behavior for $f_0 = 497.3$ Hz and thus no additional heat sources are expected to appear. Therefore, the proposed method is valid for P_i determination. Table III summarizes all $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ and P_i results, also indicating the thermal deviation in $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ among the device fingers and experimental error in P_i inferred by error propagation from this dispersion. As this table shows, the p-HEMTs with higher gate periphery (i. e., higher conducting area) exhibits higher power dissipation (1, 2 and 3), the p-HEMT 3 being the device with the highest $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ and P_i . Surprisingly, the same P_i should be

Fig. 6. $|\Delta T_{app}|$ map expressed in °C for MMIC-1 (a) and MMIC-2 (b).

obtained in p-HEMTs 1, 2 and 3 as they have the same number of fingers. This behavior can be due to a certain manufacturing dispersion related to the devices itself, the source interconnection vias, as well as the accessing pads and routing resistance or parasitics in integrated inductances, and $|\Delta T_{app,i}|$ dispersion among fingers.

As for steady state time domain thermal measurements, Fig. 7 depicts the true temperature results. As depicted in Fig. 7, the p-HEMT 3 is the most heated device in all cases and has the highest $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ values (57.8±3.4 °C/W and 24.8±1.4 °C/W for MMIC-1 and MMIC-2, respectively). From the obtained results, it is clear that the CuMo package (MMIC-2) exhibits the best thermal behavior in comparison with the Kovar (MMIC-1) one, as observed in $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ measurements.

To check whether the proposed approach allows reproducing the $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ results, (11) has been evaluated with IR results and referred to as $\overline{R_{TH(J-C),IR}}$. As a T_J^{TSP} , the average temperature of both MMICs has been considered, whereas $T_C = 75$ °C and $P = P_{tot}$ have been accounted for. As a result, 1.0 and 4.9 °C/W for MMIC-1 and MMIC-2 are obtained, respectively. The differences observed between $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ (i.e., 1.5 and 6.0 °C/W) and $\overline{R_{TH(J-C),IR}}$ mainly come from the followed procedure than experimental errors. In $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ determination, the MMIC is under ohmic regime. This operating regime differs from that of $\overline{R_{TH(J-C),IR}}$ data: the MMIC is biased under the working point

Fig. 7. True temperature map expressed in $^\circ\text{C}$ for MMIC-1 (a) and MMIC-2 (b), highlighting their maximum $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ value.

(saturation regime). In spite of this, similar values are measured, being lower for IR results. On the contrary to $R_{TH(J-C),i}$, $\overline{R_{TH(J-C)}}$ can only be used to provide an average junction temperature and not to detect hot-spots or generate temperature maps across structures with multiple heat sources. Focusing on p-HEMT 3 in MMIC-1 and MMIC-2, the temperature distribution across its fingers can be clearly distinguished, as Fig. 7 highlights. Fig. 8 depicts the IR images of the p-HEMT 3 superposed to the optical images for reference. This figure depicts that $T_{J,p-HEMT 3}^{MAX}$ of both MMICs ($97.9 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ and $85.0 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ for MMIC-1 and MMIC-2, respectively) are located under one of the gate fingers, in the middle of the device at the drain-side edge, where the highest electric field strength peak locates and, hence, the main power dissipation occurs. In that spot, heat generation is concentrated within a small volume at the p-HEMT drain-side edge of the gate contact. This occurs not only as the recombination rate becomes higher when the bias voltages (both V_{GS} and V_{DS}) increase, but also as the region of high recombination rate extends more towards the channel drain-side [42].

Fig. 8. Detail of the p-HEMT-3 device where the location of the maximum temperatures reached in the MMIC-1 (a) and MMIC-2 (b) are marked.

Each recombination process in the device generates a thermal phonon which leads to a local temperature rise [43], [36]. In such multi-finger devices, each finger acts as an independent heat source that when interact establish the following thermal pattern: the outer fingers are the coldest, whereas those in the middle are the hottest ones. In fact, $T_{J,p-HEMT 3}^{MAX}$, together with $P_{p-HEMT 3}$ and T_C , give us the value of $R_{TH(J-C),p-HEMT 3}$. Different studies about the thermal analysis of discrete AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs by means of IR thermography show that the values of the maximum $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ obtained in our work for the individual p-HEMT included in the MMIC are reasonable [36], [42], [44]. In addition, from a reliability point of view it is more interesting to consider the maximum $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ value because it determines $T_{J,i}^{MAX}$, providing a direct information on the maximum allowable values for both P_i and P_{to} [45].

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a non-invasive procedure to extract $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ in a MMIC under electrical and thermal operating condition. This method is based on the use of lock-in

thermography to extract the local dissipated power in each individual device and its temperature distribution, modulating the channels of these devices (acting as heat sources) at a specific frequency such that thermal coupling between them is avoided. With these two parameters and monitoring the MMIC backside temperature, the local thermal resistance is derived. Six different MMICs have been used as a case study featuring different package cases (Kovar and CuMo) and die-attaches. As a result, MMIC-1 and MMIC-2 were selected to carry out $R_{TH(J-C),i}$ measurements, as they were the best candidates in terms of thermal behavior: lowest average thermal resistance and best die-attached layers (according to SAMs). It has been observed from infrared measurements that the active device with the highest temperature is p-HEMT-3, which presents a thermal resistance of 57.8 ± 3.4 °C/W and 24.8 ± 1.4 °C/W depending on the used package substrate (Kovar and CuMo cases, respectively) with a relative error lower than 6%.

Notice that this method can be applied to any integrated circuit (IC), including MMICs, regardless of the semiconductor substrate material (e.g., silicon or wide bandgap). With this approach, local thermal and electrical information is provided about the electronic components monolithically integrated in the IC. Thus, this allows analyzing their behavior during operating conditions, and either optimizing their design or assessing its manufacturing in a more reliable and robust way, specially through imaging-based automatic inspection and analysis systems oriented to industry 4.0.

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